

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most typical is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Might be darkish or gentle brown (cinnamon), generally even white. Not all the time black in color. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear may be discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nevertheless, some subspecies such because the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Size: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six ft in size. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are some of the most effective at climbing timber. Their comparatively smaller size and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb timber for protection, meals, and even hibernation. The vast majority of their food plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Weight loss plan: Their various weight-reduction plan provides them the ability to live in a big vary of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They are the almost definitely bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And sure, they love honey.

The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are the most widespread of all bear species, discovered within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are responsible for almost all bear attacks in North America, with 46 per yr. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and diminished habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a big construct, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the guidelines, which led to the identify of essentially the most well-known subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt young mammals equivalent to elk and moose. Their colour varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet lengthy, and have a shoulder top of 3.3 feet. □□ Food plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on large mammals. Coastal grizzlies are typically larger than these found within the Rocky Mountains because of a richer weight-reduction plan. Every year there are forty six attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Known for his or her aggressive conduct, grizzlies are liable for probably the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are solely discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Size: Kodiak bears are almost as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, eight toes lengthy, and 4 ft tall on the shoulder. □□ Eating regimen: Their food plan is much like mainland grizzly bears. However, attributable to more plentiful meals sources, the islands can support a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to grow to be their own subspecies. This has led to a more complex social construction which results in much less battle between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears might be aggressive. Resulting from their isolation, there is only one assault on humans each other yr. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food regimen is usually made up of meat, typically from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white but is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary within the snow-coated arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and could be 7 to 10 feet tall. They're a threatened species on account of loss of habitat from local weather change. Regardless of their enormous measurement polar bears might be fast, sustaining a 6 mph tempo within the water. □□ Options: Compared to other bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, narrow head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Weight loss plan: Their eating regimen consists largely of animals, especially seals which they will scent from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is actually clear and their skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears might be extraordinarily dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Assaults are rare due to the distant nature of their habitat. Identified for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and infrequently widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account susceptible. □□ Measurement: One of the smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Weight loss program: Depending on the season it commonly feeds on small

mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on people are rising as people encroach on their habitat. □□ Harmful? They're one of the easiest bears to tame (and subsequently frequent in circuses), however Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its eating regimen is bamboo. In reality, the second person in historical past to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas defending his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body. □□ Location: Pandas are found only in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 remain within the wild and they're considered a susceptible species. □□ Measurement: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and might be over 4 toes tall, a formidable feat considering they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It also has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical pattern in mild brown and white. □□ Weight loss program: Unlike different bears the panda's eating regimen is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Features: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them regular: they poop over forty times a day! □□ Harmful? Attacks are rare however dangerous, on condition that pandas have one among the best chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It is the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is unsure but thought-about susceptible and on the decline on account of loss of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and other body elements used in traditional medicines. □□ Dimension: They stand only 39 to 55 inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They are named for his or her pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that looks like a rising sun. Additionally they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Food regimen: Sun bears tear apart bushes and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In fact, they have an extremely long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? Attributable to its shy nature, attacks are rare. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is discovered within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of lower than 20,000, they are thought-about susceptible. □□ Dimension: They're fifty five to 75 inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Options: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they are straightforward to inform aside from different Asiatic bears. In reality, they are very quick and may out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the other way up from timber. They are noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their huge curved claws. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their diet consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Harmful? They're one of the most aggressive bears, with probably the most assaults on people, largely resulting from surprise encounters. They blow the dust round with big puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 toes away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not combine properly with rhinos and elephants, typically charging at one another when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's last quick-faced bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that appear like glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Dimension: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing forty seven to seventy nine inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's final brief-confronted bear and the one bear native to South America. □□ Features: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that generally seem like glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard precious fruit and carcasses. □□ Weight loss program: Spectacled bears are mostly herbivores with a eating regimen consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, but they'll opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Dangerous? Living in distant mountains, these shy bears may be the least dangerous of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is nearer to the polar bear. They characteristic the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, similar to how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, however haven't been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA tests were unable to determine what sort of bear it was. Adorable koalas aren't bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they're indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in house. Most bear attacks occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Pink pandas? They're in their own family which can

be nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS. Watch for bear scat and bear tracks which will indicate a bear is nearby, in which case you need to be extra vigilant. Listed below are a few suggestions you can use to stop bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe. 2. MAKE NOISE. This helps bears know you are here so they do not accidentally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. KEEP YOUR DISTANCE. While you'll have great intentions, a bear is prone to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. Secure YOUR SCENTED Items (AT CAMP). If you see a bear, don't attempt to strategy or feed it. This includes food, but additionally your toiletries, for instance. Whichever methodology you choose, make certain it is at least 200 toes away from your tent so you do not appeal to bears to your campsite. 4. Keep CALM. If you happen to meet a bear, don't run. Try to make yourself look as large as attainable, waving your arms above your head. You may also prolong a jacket above your head to make yourself look larger. Lock these things in a bear canister or use a bear bag to dangle them up in a tree. Don't scream or try to scare the bear. 5. USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT). Communicate to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 ft) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward. 6. Combat Back. If all else fails and a bear attacks you, don't play useless. Which bear is the most important? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 feet long, and 4. Zero to 5.25 toes tall, the largest bear by each dimension and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Battle back with all your strength and hope that it's going to back down. Which bear is the most dangerous? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is known for the most assaults. When in bear nation, it's at all times smart to carry bear spray. It's effectively deserved, particularly when cubs are round. Every year there are approximately forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to demise. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome repute. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most likely to see an American black bear, on common there is only one attack per yr. By way of uncooked chew power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are robust and not to be messed with. When using the bite drive quotient (chew energy relative to dimension), the sun bear packs essentially the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fireplace however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he grew to become an icon and to this present day is the star of the longest-running public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has impressed numerous through-hikers to try to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a duty-free life-style. He additionally is likely to [peter rabbit teddy bear](#) be the first bear to receive his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son usually would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada near the place he was from. Chris also wrote The right way to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal elements backpacking food and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to offer fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and the way-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

